
Instilling Religious Values in Shaping the Character of Students at School

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ABSTRACT: Education not only increases students' knowledge, but instilling religious values to shape students' character is essential. The objectives of this research include: How does the education system instill religious values to shape students' character at school? How do programs shape student character? How does the process of instilling religious values in schools affect student character? How do the results of instilling religious values affect student character? This research used a qualitative approach with a natural, reasonable situation and in an authentic setting to describe phenomena and obtain accurate data related to uncovering the implementation of strategic planning in improving the quality of Islamic boarding schools and full-day schools. The research location is At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, Indonesia. The research results show that At-Tadzkir IT Middle School is an Islamic boarding school-based Integrated Islamic Middle School using a full-day education system that is part of the Indonesian Integrated Islamic School Network. The At-Tadzkir IT Middle School program can influence students' character by requiring them to board at the Islamic boarding school, build da'wah, and participate in all activities there. Meanwhile, Tazkia Insani IT Middle School has programs like Al-Quran learning, mentoring, good habits, and home visits. The religious values instilled at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School include habits, supervision, and guidance. The results of applying religious values in shaping student character are the output of students with strong faith, knowledge, and good deeds, producing preachers and people with good character.

KEYWORDS: Education, Religious Values, Students' Character, Middle School

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a system designed to improve the quality of human life (Edgerton et al., 2012; Pratomo, 2022; Rochmat et al., 2022). Human history shows that without education, no civilization is built (Ma'rifah, 2015). In other words, education will function as a tool to improve the quality of human life, transforming them from backwardness into modern humans (Hidayat et al., 2022; Mustakim, 2011; Pratomo & Kuswati, 2022). According to the national education system, education aims to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of the nation. The formation of a dignified nation is the aim of implementing education. This is demonstrated by the national education goals, which state that education in Indonesia aims to develop students into individuals who believe and fear God, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens (Puri, 2021; Santoso, 2021).

Education is an important part of human life (Fuad, 2023; Huriyah & Hidayat, 2022; Retnasari et al., 2023; Rosmalina et al., 2023); its various styles are oriented towards providing provisions for students to achieve happiness in this world and the hereafter (Fadilah et al., 2020; Rizqi et al., 2022). Therefore, Islamic education should always have its concepts and actualization updated to respond to developments in the times, which are always dynamic and temporal so that students in Islamic education are not only oriented towards the happiness of life after death, but the happiness of life in the world can also be achieved (Suroto & Jamin, 2023). Instilling religious values in students, after looking at education in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the Indonesian National Education System, states that religious education is covered in Chapter I, Article I point I (Awwaliyah & Baharun, 2019; Parker, 2017).

In Chapter I, article 1, point 1 explains the meaning of education and its aims, which cover three domains: divine, individual, and social (Awwaliyah & Baharun, 2019). This shows that education in Indonesia aims to balance the divine, the individual and the social. Education aims not only at the process of transferring culture or knowledge but also at the same time as a process of transferring values.

Good education is valuable education because human moral values are the most important in the world (Fatimah et al., 2022; Kirschenbaum, 1992; Sukatin et al., 2023; Sumarna et al., 2021). The values of conscience or life values and giving are categories of values instilled in a person and used to act and treat others wisely (Rahman et al., 2020). Conscience values include honesty, courage, love of peace, loyalty, personal potential, discipline, awareness of boundaries, purity, and conformity (Sari & Isnaini,

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2021; Zahrah, 2021). On the other hand, the values of giving must be applied or given to others, who will then receive as much value as is given. Therefore, they must be loyal, reliable, respectful, loving, affectionate, sensitive, unselfish, friendly, fair and generous.

Forming a child's character must start from an early age (Sutisno et al., 2023), namely from infancy to adolescence because character formation takes a long time and can only be done slowly (Kustinah et al., 2022; Windayani et al., 2021). Adolescence is the most difficult part of the formation process, because it is a period of searching for one's identity (Rosmalina et al., 2023). In addition, adolescence is a very important period in forming values (Azimovna, 2020). One of the characteristics of teenagers related to values is that they are aware of the importance of values and develop the new values they need to help them find their path. Therefore, adolescence is a problem for the government and society. Education and development are also a concern for parents. This problem requires special attention so that the guidance is based on the characteristics of teenagers experiencing a crisis and inner turmoil. Even though periods of crisis and inner shock are temporary, these temporary characteristics influence teenagers when faced with teaching, especially religious education.

Educating a religious child is obligatory for every Muslim. Both parents are guilty if their child is not religious until they become true Muslims. Rasulullah SAW has given instructions to Muslims to provide religious education and character education to each of their children. The instillation of values in education varies greatly depending on the educational institution that designs what values it wants to instil (Kuliyatun, 2020). The aim of instilling values is for everyone who experiences education to develop and become good at living his life (Indriyani, 2022).

Educational institutions, in this case schools, must have a mission to create a school culture that is challenging and fun, fair, creative, innovative, integrated (Paulus et al., 2021) and dedicated to achieving the vision, producing graduates who are of high quality and have the character of purity, honesty, creativity, able to be role models, work hard, be tolerant and competent in leading, and answer the challenges of the need to develop human resources who can play a role in the development of science and technology based on faith and piety. Educational institutions must implement character formation during the learning process (Abdurakhman et al., 2022; Handayani & Hasanah, 2020; Ulfa et al., 2021). One way to shape the character of students is by instilling religious values (Rachman et al., 2023; Retnasari et al., 2023; Wening & Hasanah, 2020). However, further research is needed on the educational institutions involved to determine how this process persists. Students are subjects and objects who need guidance from others to direct their potential and guide them towards maturity with personality and character. It is hoped that consistently instilling character values can produce students with character and morals who can realize positive standards and values in their educational success.

The background of the description above can be found when entering the At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School environment; from here, we can see that religious values are embedded in them. This can be seen in the students' polite behavior, greetings, and clothing by Islamic law. Apart from that, the unique thing about these schools is the many achievements of students even though the schools have just been founded, and also that both are IT junior high schools, both of them also have different histories. At-Tadzkir IT Middle School collaborates with Islamic boarding schools, while Tazkia Insani IT Middle School collaborates with day-to-day schools. Therefore, further research is needed in scientific development regarding the instillation of religious values in shaping students' character.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted in a natural, reasonable situation and in an authentic setting to describe phenomena and obtain accurate data related to uncovering the implementation of strategic planning in improving the quality of Islamic boarding schools and full-day schools. This research was carried out using a qualitative approach. The author adopts qualitative research using a case study approach to collect data and gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon. Case study research is focused on only one selected phenomenon and wants to be understood in depth while ignoring other phenomena. The research location is At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, Indonesia. The subjects studied were students, parents, teachers, boarding school administrators, staff, and the head. The analytical method used in this research is descriptive analysis to describe events, people's behavior, or a situation in narrative form in more depth and detail.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

1. Education System at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School

In principle, the education system at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School has its characteristics regarding the curriculum used. SMP IT At-Tadzkir is based on an Islamic boarding school with the Qadariyah Naqsabandiyah ideology by combining the curriculum from the education service with the Islamic boarding school. What is highlighted by At-Tadzkir IT Middle School is the field of Da'wah; this is proven in the achievements students get when participating in speech or da'wah competitions, always becoming champions.

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Meanwhile, Tazkia Insani IT Middle School is a middle school that uses a full-day school system under the auspices of the Indonesian Integrated Islamic School Network (JSIT), where the curriculum automatically combines the official and JSIT curricula. The advantage of schools with a full-day school system is that the integration and interaction of students with teachers are more intense; they prioritize students' morals and academic achievements, they get a complete education, and Students' potential interests and talents are channeled through extracurricular activities.

From the description above, the education system used at the two schools, namely SMP IT AT-Tadzkir and SMP IT Tazkia Insani, has participated in carrying out national education, which has the aim of building abilities and forming character, thus making students moral human beings. Noble and contribute to helping achieve the goals of character education that the government has proclaimed.

2. Program to Instill Religious Values in Shaping the Character of Students at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School

The religious values instillation program that is instilled at the At-Tadzkir IT SMP can be seen from the education system used, namely the Islamic boarding school-based IT SMP. Some of the programs at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School include the following.

a. Require students to board at Islamic boarding schools

The education program at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School is an Islamic boarding school-based middle school, meaning students who enter this school must be in an Islamic boarding school even though their house is right near the Islamic boarding school environment. Due to this, IT Middle School students are also at this Islamic boarding school. In other words, when students live in Islamic boarding schools, the students at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School will receive guidance and guidance at all times in Islamic boarding schools so that the goals of Islamic education will be easy to achieve.

b. Build Da'wah

Build Da'wah is a superior program from the Islamic boarding school and the At-Tadzkir IT Middle School, where students are trained to become preachers. This da'wah development is part of the general subject at school and is studied from class VII to class IX. Build Da'wah is also carried out in two languages, namely English and Arabic. Besides learning about religious teaching materials, students also learn to get used to speaking in English and Arabic. The great hope of the Build Da'wah program is that Islamic boarding schools and schools can produce a cadre of reliable preachers with noble morals.

c. Require students to participate in all boarding school activities.

Students who are also students are required to take part in every activity both at school and at the Islamic boarding school so that it will be easy for students to understand the learning process at school and vice versa during the learning process at the Islamic boarding school. This is a form of school and Islamic boarding school's efforts to educate and teach students to have general knowledge and religious knowledge so that it leads to the goal of making students who have good morals.

The program for cultivating religious values instilled at SMP IT Tazkia Insani can be seen from the three curriculum concepts previously stated above. SMP IT Tazkia Insani has also created and implemented superior programs with the Integrated Islamic school curriculum. These programs also lead to one goal, namely the formation of students' character, including the following.

a. Reading the Al-Qur'an

This Al-Qur'an learning activity aims to bring students closer, increase their faith in Allah SWT and the Al-Qur'an, and train students' discipline and consistency in carrying out a job. From the Al-Qur'an learning process, not only can students read and memorize the Al-Qur'an well and correctly, but students are also expected to have a sense of responsibility, discipline, competence, and criticality to make students have good personality and character.

b. Separating Islamic History material from Islamic Religious Education lessons

The separation of Islamic history material from Islamic Religious Education lessons is based on several factors, including many historical materials in Islamic Religious Education lessons that are not conveyed to students. This is caused by a lack of class time, so it needs to be increased. The purpose of separating Islamic history material from Islamic Religious Education lessons is to introduce students to Muslim figures. It comes down to examples from the figures themselves, so they don't use teaching materials like other subjects but directly from the original sources.

c. Mentoring

Mentoring activities are carried out every Friday by providing students with religious materials. This mentoring activity aims to build students' personalities so that they have a clean creed, correct worship, Islamic morals, good self-management, good time management, a strong and healthy physique, a complete understanding of Islam, good self-discipline, good communication skills, Islamic brotherhood, responsibility, independence, empathy, honesty, etc.

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d. Habituation of noble character

This character-building activity is included in all activities at Tazkia Insani IT Middle School and is an extracurricular program. Supervision and character development are not only the tasks of Islamic Religious Education teachers, but all teachers must shape the morals of students.

e. Home visit

This program is a form of activity that involves collaboration between teaching staff at schools and parents of students. The activity is to visit students' homes to hold discussions with parents regarding student development, both at school and home, and also to discuss problem-solving if problems occur with students.

3. The Process of Instilling Religious Values in Shaping the Character of Students at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School

Character formation of students at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School through example, habituation, advice, supervision, and punishment. This process is carried out by involving all parties within each school. The following describes the process of instilling religious values in shaping students' character.

a. Exemplary

The example applied by the teachers and caregivers at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School is in terms of worship to get closer to Allah. There are activities to carry out obligatory congregational prayers, Duha prayers, and religious services by the Qadariyah Naqshabandiyah Order. In terms of this example, the teachers and caretakers of the boarding school are consistently consistent in jointly providing an example to students.

The example applied by Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, namely setting an example of noble character. Educators and educational staff provide examples of good morals, with methods and attitudes that uphold tolerance of others, respect elders, speak kind words, and wear Muslim clothing for women and Muslim clothing for men.

Based on this description, the example at IT At-Tadzkir IT Middle School and Tazkia Insani IT Middle School is in realizing religious values using parents, teachers, boarding school caregivers, and all staff at schools and Islamic boarding schools providing examples or role models for their students in how to speak politely, behaving well, doing something how to worship, and so on. Therefore, students can see, witness, and believe in the natural way so that students can carry it out better and more efficiently.

b. Habituation

Routine activities carried out in the process of instilling values at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School are through the learning process at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School, which is carried out starting from 07.30 WIB – 13.15 WIB, then from 15.30 WIB – 21.30 WIB taking part in learning at the Islamic boarding school.

Routine activities are carried out in the process of instilling values at Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, namely by regularly scheduled activities starting from 07.00 WIB to 15.30 WIB. In the process, apart from delivering the material, each subject teacher must synergize the values that can ultimately be implemented in everyday life.

c. Advice

At At-Tadzkir IT Middle School, all the teachers advise students directly and indirectly. Advice is given during the learning process. This advice is provided at no specific scheduled time but is conditional in nature.

At Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, advice is given directly through a coaching process called Islamic Personal Development (BPI). Islamic Personal Development is part of the curriculum provided by the Indonesian Integrated Islamic School Network (JSIT). Islamic Personal Development discusses material that has not been covered in Islamic religious education subjects..

d. Supervision

The supervision process at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School requires all students to live in the dormitory provided by the Islamic boarding school. Therefore, the supervision process takes place 24 hours per day by teachers working with the Islamic boarding school caregivers. This process makes it very easy to supervise students.

Tazkia Insani IT Middle School supervises its students through monitoring activities during the learning process. This supervision is carried out in collaboration with parents. Teachers carry out supervision in the school environment and report various developments experienced by students to parents, while parents or guardians supervise students outside the school environment and communicate and report various developments to teachers.

e. Give punishment

Punishments given to students when they make mistakes or violations at the At-Tadzkir IT Middle School are handled by the OSIS (Intra-School Student Organization). At the same time, the boarding school administrators take students who violate boarding school regulations.

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Meanwhile, the OSIS administrators handle the punishment and discipline at the Tazkia Insani IT Middle School if the violation is still in the mild category. Meanwhile, crucial forms of violations are handled directly by a special team, namely the disciplinary commission.

4. Results of Instilling Religious Values in Shaping the Character of Students at School

At the At-Tadzkir IT Middle School, which is based on an Islamic boarding school, the results of instilling religious values include: 1) Emphasis on these three aspects of values, namely creed values, moral values, and shariah values, is a program that is developed. It is hoped that it will be by the vision of SMP IT At-Tadzkir, which is to create a school with faith, knowledge, and charity. 2) The expected output from this school is an individual who has a strong faith, high knowledge, and good deeds.

Meanwhile, at Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, which uses the full-day school system, the results of instilling religious values include: 1) The developed program emphasizes moral values only more. This can be seen in instilling exemplary religious values, habituation, advice, attention/supervision, and punishment. Even though these five processes are implemented, the emphasis is on moral values. 2) The expected output from this school is to become students with good character.

B. DISCUSSION

With the results of this research, there are several recommendations regarding cultivating religious values in shaping students' character. In instilling religious values in shaping students' character, all parties should be involved, including teachers, management staff in the school environment, Islamic boarding school, and the family environment, so that character is formed among the school's academic community. To examine the instillation of religious values in shaping students' character, researchers should pay attention to more than just the education system, programs developed, and the implementation process. Still, they must also pay attention to who is involved in implementing the instillation of religious values. Recommendations for further research are that the research conducted in this study only revealed a small part of the problems related to the instillation of spiritual values in shaping students' character. In other words, many other factors still need to be revealed. For this reason, it is recommended that further researchers carry out further and structured studies so that this can be carried out better.

CONCLUSIONS

Religious values shape students' character at school, including the following: 1) At-Tadzkir IT Middle School is an Islamic boarding school that uses the 2013 curriculum and the Islamic boarding school curriculum. Tadzkia Insani IT Middle School is included in the Indonesian Integrated Islamic School Network (JSIT) and uses the education service curriculum; 2) At-Tadzkir IT Middle School carries out a program to instill religious values in shaping the character of its students through activities such as requiring students to board at Islamic boarding schools, building da'wah, and requiring students to take part in all Islamic boarding school activities. Meanwhile at Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, the religious values instillation program includes Al-Quran learning, mentoring, and familiarization; 3) The process of instilling religious values at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School shapes student character through example (exemplary Kiai and teachers); habituation (routine study, Duha prayer, congregational prayer, and practice by the Qadariyah Naqsabandiyah Tariqat); advice; supervision (24 hours a day); and punishment; 4) The results of the application of religious values in shaping the character of students at At-Tadzkir IT Middle School. The emphasis is on three aspects of output: individuals who have strong faith, knowledge, and good deeds, and producing a preacher. At Tazkia Insani IT Middle School, the emphasis is on the moral aspect of output, which makes individuals have good character and become preachers.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abdurakhman, R. N., Lawej, A. I., & Herlina, N. (2022). The Influence of Project-Based Outdoor Learning Activities on Children's Independence Development. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 1(2), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqq.v1i2.15>
- 2) Awwaliyah, R., & Baharun, H. (2019). Pendidikan Islam dalam sistem pendidikan nasional (Telaah epistemologi terhadap problematika pendidikan Islam). *JURNAL ILMIAH DIDAKTIKA: Media Ilmiah Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran*, 19(1), 34–49.
- 3) Azimovna, F. M. (2020). Formation of spiritual and moral values of pupils in physical education lessons. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 9(11), 99–103. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00280.3>
- 4) Edgerton, J. D., Roberts, L. W., & von Below, S. (2012). Education and Quality of Life. In *Handbook of Social Indicators and Quality of Life Research* (pp. 265–296). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2421-1_12
- 5) Fadilah, R., Parinduri, S. A., Syaimi, K. U., & Suharyanto, A. (2020). Islamic Guidance and Counseling to Overcome The Study Difficulty of Junior High School Students in SMP IT Nurul Azizi Medan (Case Study of Students Experiencing Anxiety). *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24, 1154–1160.

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- 6) Fatimah, S., Rosidin, D. N., & Hidayat, A. (2022). Student-based Learning in The Perspective of Constructivism Theory and Maieutics Method. *International Journal Of Social Science And Human Research*, 5(5), 1632–1637.
- 7) Fuad, V. (2023). Relationship between Young Citizens Democracy Education and Good Governance. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 2(1), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v2i1.41>
- 8) Handayani, F., & Hasanah, A. (2020). Model pengelolaan pendidikan karakter di sekolah pada masa pandemi. *Fastabiq: Jurnal Studi Islam*, 1(2), 145–156.
- 9) Hidayat, A., Fatimah, S., & Rosidin, D. N. (2022). Challenges and Prospects of Islamic Education Institutions and Sustainability in The Digital Era. *Nazhruna: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 5(2), 351–366.
- 10) Huriyah, H., & Hidayat, A. (2022). SECTIONS Model Analysis for Pre-service English Teachers' Media Selection in Pandemic Covid 19. *International Journal of Instruction*, 15(3), 599–610. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2022.15333a>
- 11) Indriyani, L. T. (2022). Internalization of Islamic Education Values for Children with Special Needs. *Journal of Media, Culture and Communication*, 24, 7–15. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jmcc24.7.15>
- 12) Kirschenbaum, H. (1992). A comprehensive model for values education and moral education. *The Phi Delta Kappan*, 73(10), 771–776.
- 13) Kuliyyatun, K. (2020). PENANAMAN NILAI-NILAI RELIGIUS PADA PESERTA DIDIK DI SMA MUHAMMADIYAH 01 METRO LAMPUNG. *At-Tajdid : Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pemikiran Islam*, 3(2), 180. <https://doi.org/10.24127/att.v3i2.1126>
- 14) Kustinah, E., Kambali, K., & Lama'atushabakh, M. (2022). Humanistic Counseling and Student Learning Motivation. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 1(2), 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v1i2.19>
- 15) Ma'rifah, S. (2015). Pesantren Sebagai Habitus Peradaban Islam Indonesia. *JURNAL PENELITIAN*, 9(2), 347. <https://doi.org/10.21043/jupe.v9i2.1325>
- 16) Mustakim, B. (2011). Pendidikan karakter: membangun delapan karakter emas menuju Indonesia bermartabat. *Samudra Biru*.
- 17) Parker, L. (2017). Religious environmental education? The new school curriculum in Indonesia. *Environmental Education Research*, 23(9), 1249–1272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2016.1150425>
- 18) Paulus, K., Irsyadiah, N., & Rifa'i, A. (2021). Affirmation of School Management and Success of Islamic Religious Education Learning. *Journal of Social Science*, 2(2), 162–175.
- 19) Pratomo, H. W. (2022). Educational Leadership: Islamic Religious, Philosophy, Psychology, and Sociology Perspectives. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 05(05). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i5-26>
- 20) Pratomo, H. W., & Kuswati, Y. (2022). The Effect of Teacher Motivation on Student Achievement in Islamic Senior High School. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 1(2), 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v1i2.17>
- 21) Puri, M. P. (2021). Character education and citizenship education in the middle of community. *IJOIS: Indonesian Journal of Islamic Studies*, 2(2), 117–126.
- 22) Rachman, A., Kawakip, A. N., Fadhillah, F., Saputra, N., & Zulkifli, Z. (2023). Building Religious Character of Students in Madrasah Through Moral Learning. *Tafkir: Interdisciplinary Journal of Islamic Education*, 4(1), 78–94.
- 23) Rahman, M. H., Kencana, R., & NurFaizah, S. P. (2020). Pengembangan nilai moral dan agama anak usia dini: panduan bagi orang tua, guru, mahasiswa, dan praktisi PAUD. *Edu Publisher*.
- 24) Retnasari, L., Hakim, A. P., Hermawan, H., & Prasetyo, D. (2023). Cultivating Religious Character through School Culture. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 2(1), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v2i1.29>
- 25) Rizqi, R. M. F., Herdi, H. W. P., & Udin, N. A. (2022). The Educational Role of Majelis Ta'lim Al-Mubaroq in an Effort to Increase Community Worship in Cijati Village, Majalengka Regency. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 1(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v1i1.1>
- 26) Rochmat, C. S., Yoranita, A. S. P., & Putri, H. A. (2022). Islamic Boarding School Educational Values in Efforts to Realize Student Life Skills at University of Darussalam Gontor. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 1(2), 6–15. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v1i2.18>
- 27) Rosmalina, A., Elrahman, H., Handayani, H., & Affendi, H. (2023). Islamic Mental Health Education for Adolescents in the Digital Era. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 2(1), 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v2i1.39>
- 28) Santoso, G. (2021). The Philosophical Power of Civic Education 21st Century in Indonesia. *IJEBD (International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business Development)*, 4(1), 72–79.
- 29) Sari, D. C., & Isnaini, L. (2021). The Education Characters Using Local Wisdom Approach. *International Journal of Applied Guidance and Counseling*, 2(1), 20–25.

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- 30) Sukatin, S., Munawwaroh, S., Emilia, E., & Sulistyowati, S. (2023). Pendidikan Karakter dalam Dunia Pendidikan. *Anwarul*, 3(5), 1044–1054.
- 31) Sumarna, C., Djubaedi, D., Fatimah, S., Mas'ud, A., Rosidin, D. N., & Hidayat, A. (2021). Multicultural Value of Education in Forming the Community's Religious Attitude. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Multidisciplinary Topics*, 2(8), 168–171.
- 32) Suroto, S., & Jamin, H. (2023). Actualization of Islamic Education Today in the Perspective of Muhammad Naquib Al-Attas' Thought. *ISTIFHAM: Journal Of Islamic Studies*, 167–174.
- 33) Sutisno, A. N., Novianawati, N., & Hidayatullah, M. A. S. (2023). Domestic Waste Management Strategy through Realization of School Waste Banks towards Students Scientific Behavior. *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, 2(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.58418/ijeqqr.v2i1.22>
- 34) Ulfa, E., Djubaedi, D., Sumarna, C., Fatimah, S., Suklani, S., & Hidayat, A. (2021). The Role of Teachers in Fostering Religious Multiculturalism. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(10), 349–354.
- 35) Wening, M. H., & Hasanah, E. (2020). Strategies for developing religious culture to shape, the character of students. *International Journal of Educational Management and Innovation*, 1(3), 262–270.
- 36) Windayani, N. L. I., Dewi, N. W. R., Yuliantini, S., Widiasanti, N. P., Ariyana, I. K. S., Keban, Y. B., Mahartini, K. T., Dafiq, N., & Ayu, P. E. S. (2021). Teori dan aplikasi pendidikan anak usia dini. Yayasan Penerbit Muhammad Zaini.
- 37) Zahrah, N. F. (2021). An Analysis of The Values Character Education in Film "Finding Nemo. Institut Agama Islam Negeri Madura.